

Guide to open access pub- lishing

At no cost to

the reader or author

In this guide, you'll find a wide selection of diamond journals, which offer various options for publishing your results in an Open Access environment, at no cost to the reader or the author.

Open publishing practices are crucial in a context where free access to research results is essential for knowledge sharing and innovation.

The traditional publishing model restricts reader access, while Open Access gold and hybrid allow free access to research, but charge authors. While these models improve accessibility, they ultimately shift the publication cost to researchers, creating further constraints.

New, fairer options are emerging, like the diamond publishing model. This lets authors and readers publish and access research for free. Funded by academic institutions, the diamond pathway is a sustainable way to share knowledge.

Information contact:

Valentina Caracuta

Librarian - Open Science specialist

www.hesge.ch/hepia/bibliotheque/open-science

Environmental Sciences

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Engineering

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Technology

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Physical Sciences

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Interdisciplinary

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Environ- mental Sciences

Aerosol Research (AR)

Engineering Environmental science

LANGUAGE English
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PUBLISHER Copernicus Publications, GERMANY
ISSN 2940-3391

Afrique durable 2030

Agriculture Sustainability

LANGUAGE French
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PUBLISHER Association Africa 21, SWITZERLAND
ISSN 2673-7396

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Aquaculture Fisheries Angling

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ISSN 1765-2952

Cahiers Agricultures

Agriculture Ecology

LANGUAGE French
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ISSN 1777-5949

Ciência e Técnica Vitivinícola / Journal of Viticulture and Enology

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ISSN 2416-395

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Agriculture Sustainability

LANGUAGE English ; French ; German
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PUBLISHER Schweizerische Gesellschaft für Agrarwirtschaft und Agrarsoziologie, SWITZERLAND
ISSN 1023-3938

BASE - Biotechnologie, Agronomie, Société et Environnement / Biotechnology, Agronomy, Society and Environment

Agriculture Ecology

LANGUAGE English ; French
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PUBLISHER University of Liège, BELGIUM
ISSN 1780-4507

BAUHINIA : Basler Botanisch Gesellschaft

Plant science

LANGUAGE English ; German
LICENSE Other
PUBLISHER Botanische Gesellschaft Basel, SWITZERLAND
ISSN 0067-4605

Biosystematics and Ecology (BiosystEcol)

Biosystematics Ecology

LANGUAGE English
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PUBLISHER Austrian Academy of Sciences, AUSTRIA
ISSN 2710-298X

Bulletin de l'Association de Géographes Français

Geography Statistics Landscape

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PUBLISHER Association de géographes français, FRANCE
ISSN 2275-5195

Bulletin de la Société Vaudoise des Sciences Naturelles

Life Sciences Biomedicine Other topics

LANGUAGE English ; French
LICENSE Other
PUBLISHER Société Vaudoise des Sciences Naturelles, SWITZERLAND
ISSN 0037-9603

Caucasiana : Journal on the biodiversity of the Caucasus and the adjacent regions

Biosystematics Ecology

LANGUAGE English
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ISSN 2667-9809

Comptes Rendus Géoscience

Earth sciences

LANGUAGE English ; French
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PUBLISHER Académie des Sciences, FRANCE
ISSN 1778-7025

Comptes Rendus Palevol

Evolution Palaeontology

LANGUAGE English ; French
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PUBLISHER Académie des Sciences, FRANCE
ISSN 1777-571X

Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift

Entomology

LANGUAGE English ; German
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EID - Environnement, Ingénierie & Développement

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LANGUAGE English ; French
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ISSN 2778-844X

Estuarine Management and Technologies

Water management Engineering

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ISSN 3033-022X

Evolutionary Systematics

Biosystematics Evolution

LANGUAGE English ; German
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ISSN 2535-0730

Food and Ecological Systems Modelling Journal

Agriculture Mathematic

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Fossil Record

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Geography

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INRAE Productions Animales

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IVES Conference Series

Enology Viticulture

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PUBLISHER International Viticulture & Enology Society, FRANCE
ISSN 2777-9173

IVES Technical Reviews

Enology Viticulture

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ISSN 2019-9999

J3eA - Journal sur l'enseignement des sciences et technologies de l'information et des systèmes

Computer science Education

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Agriculture

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ISSN 1867-0938

Journal of Orthoptera Research

Entomology

LANGUAGE English
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PUBLISHER Orthopterists' Society, LUXEMBOURG
ISSN 1937-2426

Journal of Plant Hydraulics

Ecology Plant science

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ISSN 2426-413X

KMAE - Knowledge and Management of Aquatic Ecosystems / Bulletin français de la pêche et de la pisciculture

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Le Naturaliste canadien *

Biology Water management

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Engineering Environmental science

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New Zealand Journal of Forestry Science

Ecology

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ISSN 1179-5395

OCL - Oilseeds and fats, Crops and Lipids

Agronomy Biochemistry

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OENO One

Enology Viticulture

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ISSN 2016-9999

OWL - Open Wine Law (vine and wine law open access journal)

Enology Viticulture Law

LANGUAGE English ; French
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Pachyderm

Zoology

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PARKS - The International Journal of Protected Areas and Conservation

Zoology

LANGUAGE English
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ted Areas (WCPA), SWITZERLAND
ISSN 2411-2119

Peer Community Journal

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Palaeontology Wood science

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Evolution Ecology

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Botanical Society of Belgium,
BELGIUM
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FRANCE
ISSN 1969-6124

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Agriculture

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ISSN 2813-317X

Revue de Paléobiologie

Evolution Ecology Zoology Botany

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SWITZERLAND
ISSN 0253-6730

Revue des Sciences de l'Eau / Journal of Water Science

Water management Hydrobiology
(Eco)toxicology

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CANADA
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Ecology Zoology Wood science

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Revue Organisations & Territoires

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CANADA
ISSN 2564-2189

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Silva Balcanica

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Forest Research Institute, BULGARIA

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Ecology Urbanism Planification

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Zoology Entomology Evolution

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VDJ : Viticulture Data Journal

Viticulture Software

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VITIS - Journal of Grapevine Research

Enology Viticulture

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Grapevine Breeding Geilweilerhof,
GERMANY

ISSN 2367-4156

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Evolution Ecology

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ISSN 1399-1183

Zitteliana : An International Journal of Palaeontology and Geology

Evolution Palaeontology

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of Palaeontology and Geology
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Engi- neering

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Mechanics Acoustic Computer science

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Acta Polytechnica CTU Proceedings

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Ambiances : Environnement Sensible, Architecture et Espace Urbain

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ISSN 2101-0714

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Civil Engineering Journal

Civil engineering Mechanics

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Energy

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Medicine Engineering Ecology

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Chemistry Material science

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Building construction Project management

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Architecture Urbanism Landscape

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Transportation

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Engineering Environmental science

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ISSN	1969-6124

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Water Management Hydrobiology (Eco)toxicology

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Roadsides

Transportation

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ISSN	2624-9081

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RSC Sustainability**

Sustainability Chemistry Transportation

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Technè*

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ISSN 2409-0026

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ISSN 2409-9708

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PUBLISHER European Alliance for Innovation (EAI), BELGIUM
ISSN 2410-0218

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Computer science

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Computer science Gouvernance

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ISSN 2032-9393

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Computer science Engineering Energy

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SLOVENIA
ISSN 1854-3871

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Università di Genova, ITALY
ISSN 2384-8766

IJVR - International Journal of Virtual Reality

Computer science Virtual reality

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Computer science Humanities

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JMLR - Journal of Machine Learning Research

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JOT - Journal of Object Technology

Computer science

LANGUAGE English
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les Technologies Objets (AITO),
SWITZERLAND
ISSN 1660-1769

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Computer science Statistic

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Statistics, USA
ISSN 1548-7660

Logical Methods in Computer Science

Computer science

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Science e.V., GERMANY
ISSN 1860-5974

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Geomechanics

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PUBLISHER ALERT Geomaterials - Alliance of
Laboratories in Europe for Edu-
cation, Research and Technology,
FRANCE
ISSN 2644-9676

Open Journal of Mathematical Optimization

Computer science Mathematics

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ISSN 2777-5860

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Mathematics Computer science

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sion de la recherche francophone
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ISSN 2967-9672

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Computer science Cyber security

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CANADA

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GERMANY

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ISSN pending

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Mathematics

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AutoRicerca

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